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Palladium-Catalyzed Regioselective Synthesis of 3-(Hetero)Arylpropynamides from gem-Dibromoalkenes and Isocyanides

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Abstract

An alternative method related to the formation of 3(hetero)arylpropynamides using palladium/Cs₂CO₃, the regiochemically-controlled coupling of isocyanides with 1,1dibromo-1-alkenes is described.

Keywords: 3-Propynamides; Cross-coupling reaction; Isocyanides; 1,1-Dibromo-1-alkenes, Palladium acetate; Tandem reaction.